

MITIGATING SEASONALITY IN TOURISM

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Abstract

Seasonality is a widely recognised and accredited phenomenon known to cause an imbalance of tourism activity throughout the year, prompting tourist destinations, both public and private, to consider how best to plan the use of their resources. One way of mitigating the economic imbalances that seasonality can cause is to find strategies for seasonal adjustment, such as travel programmes aimed at the elderly. This paper analyses the seasonality of tourism activity in Spain, in the period from January 2001 to December 2019. The study then focuses on tourism programmes for the elderly in Spain to see whether this type of programmes help to alleviate the seasonality of tourism activity. To corroborate this, an econometric model is specified and estimated which enables the scope of these programmes to be compared. The results obtained show that these programmes are effective in reducing tourism seasonality.

Keywords: Seasonality, tourism demand, tourism supply, Gini coefficient.

1. Introduction

Butler (1994, 2001) defines seasonality in tourism activity as a temporary imbalance, in which both supply and demand are involved. Tourism seasonality is understood as the concentration of flows and tourist activity in a certain period of the year (Lage & Milone, 2000). It describes the temporary mismatch between supply and demand and the subsequent imbalances between the coming and going of tourists.

Tourism seasonality has social, economic, and environmental consequences, most of them negative. This wide scope of issues has prompted a prolific number of studies as shown in a review of the scientific literature.

Despite the interest in analysing the impact, implications, and the proposals for managing seasonality in tourism activity, the complexity of the problem itself makes it difficult for those responsible for planning tourist destinations to reach a consensus on how best to tackle the problem.

The aim of this study is, on the one hand, to quantify the seasonality of tourism activity in Spain, both in terms of supply and demand and, on the other hand, to analyse and quantify the impact of applying seasonal adjustment measures, such as the programmes offered by the Institute for the Elderly and Social Services (Imsero).

The study of seasonality is carried out using the Gini coefficient (GC) for each of the years in the period considered. To examine the effectiveness of the programme developed by Imserso in reducing the seasonality of tourism activity in Spain, an econometric model is specified in which the endogenous variable is the variation of GC of tourism activity in the Spanish regions and as explanatory factors the number of travellers in hotel establishments assigned to the Imserso Social Tourism Programme and the value of the subsidy of the programme.

2. Data

The information comes essentially from two sources. The INE provides relevant data on tourism activity for the period from January 2001 to December 2019. Finally, the information from Imserso is used to assess whether this tourism policy measure applied in Spain contributes to reducing the seasonality of activity of the tourism sector.

The study of seasonality is carried out from a double perspective. From the point of view of demand, the number of travellers in hotel establishments, pensions, hostels, rural houses, and campsites (hereafter referred to collectively as hotel establishments) is used as an indicator. The six tourist destinations considered are the regions of Andalusia, the Balearic Islands, the Canary Islands, Catalonia, the Valencian Community and Murcia Region. From the point of view of supply, the following indicators are considered, among others: the number of tourist establishments that are open and the number of places available.

The Spanish government is aware of the significance of seasonality in tourism activity, and the consequent repercussions on production and the labour market and has therefore decided on a set of measures to promote tourism in periods of less tourism activity. One of these initiatives is the Active Ageing Programme for the elderly offered by Imserso and on which this study focuses.

The Active Ageing Programme provides the elderly with the possibility of accessing holidays, at a reduced price, in areas with warm climates and which offer localised cultural tours of places of interest. The main objectives of the programme are: 1. To improve the quality of life of the elderly and, 2. To favour the creation or maintenance of employment in the tourism sector.

3. Methodology

Seasonality coefficients

In order to quantify the degree of seasonality in tourism activity, six different seasonality coefficients: coefficients of variation (CV), Gini (GC), Markham (MC), Walsh-Lawler (WLC), Oliver (OC) and Entropy (EC) are used in most of the scientific

literature that deals with tourism seasonality. However, in this paper only GC is used because the correlation with the other coefficients is very high¹.

The value of the indicator considered in the month i of year j is denoted as x_{ij} ; thus, $x_j = \sum_{i=1}^{12} x_{ij}$ represents the annual total of the tourism indicator for the year j ; and the average monthly value for the year j is $\bar{x}_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{12} x_{ij}}{12}$. Similarly, the variance and standard deviation of the indicator are defined, as is usual, as $\sigma_{x_j}^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{12} (x_{ij} - \bar{x}_j)^2}{12}$ y $\sigma_{x_j} = \sqrt{\sigma_{x_j}^2}$, respectively.

Gini coefficient² (GC) (Gini, 1912) for year j is calculated using the following expression:

$$GC_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{12-1} (p_i - q_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^{12-1} p_i} \quad (1)$$

where p_i represents the cumulative percentage of the months of the year (1/12, 2/12, ...) and q_i the accumulated percentage of the indicator of tourism activity in each of the months (rearranged) within year j . If there is no seasonality in a tourist destination, that is, if the tourist flow is the same each month, the coefficients p_i and q_i coincide in all months of the year, so the GC statistic would be equal to zero. On the contrary, if all tourism activity is concentrated in a single month, i , it is evident that, for that month, the value of q_i would be equal to 1, but for remaining months the q_i coefficients would be equal to zero, so the GC would reach the value of 1.

Econometric model

To verify the effectiveness or validity of the tourism policy measures overseen by the Ministry of Social Rights and Agenda 2030 in Spain, through the Imsero Social Tourism Programme, an econometric model is specified to corroborate whether the programme has contributed to the reduction of seasonality in tourism activity in Spain.

The analysis is carried out both from the perspective of demand and of supply. From the perspective of demand, *the number of travellers in hotel establishments* is used, while from the perspective of supply, *the number of hotel establishments that are open* is used, which reflects the capacity to receive tourists, in each of the tourist destinations considered.

The equation of the econometric model to analyse seasonality from the demand perspective is:

¹ The range of values of correlation coefficients is from 0.96 to 0.99.

² Before calculating GC, the values of the indicator of tourism activity needed to be ordered from lowest to highest value, within each year.

$$\log(GC_{dt}^D) = \beta_1 \log(GC_{dt-1}^D) + \beta_2 \log(V_{IMS_{dt}}) + \beta_3 \log(V_{IMS_{dt-1}}) + \beta_4 \log(P_{IMS_{dt}}) + \beta_5 \log(P_{IMS_{dt-1}}) + \sum_{d=1}^6 \gamma_d DTUR_d + u_{dt} \quad (2)$$

The variable GC_{dt}^D measures the degree or intensity of seasonality of each of the tourist destinations, ($d = 1, 2, \dots, 6$), throughout the entire period analysed, which goes from 2001 to 2019, ($t = 1, 2, \dots, 19$). This gives 114 observations for the variable GC_{dt}^D , when considering the six tourist destinations over the nineteen-year period.

The efficiency of the *Imsero* programme is measured through two variables. The first variable, denoted as $V_{IMS_{dt}}$, corresponds to the *number of beneficiaries or travellers in hotel establishments subsidised by Imsero*. The second variable used, $P_{IMS_{dt}}$, represents the *value of the subsidy by Imsero*. To homogenise the price variable, throughout the sample period, it has been deflated using the CPI of hotel establishments and restaurants.

From the economic point of view, the regression coefficient obtained for the variable *number of travellers in hotel establishments subsidised by Imsero* is expected to present a negative sign. This indicates that, as the number of travellers increases in periods of low tourist demand, the intensity of seasonality decreases. However, the regression coefficient that affects the variable *value of the subsidy* is also expected to present a negative sign, since when the *value of the subsidy* decreases, there will be less demand on the part of the potential beneficiaries of the programme, causing an increase in the degree of seasonality.

Lastly, the variables $DTUR_d$, which are six *dummies* variables, collect the effect in each of the tourist destinations. Thus, each one of them takes the value 1 according to the corresponding tourist destination, and 0 in the other cases.

The econometric model specified to analyse seasonality from the supply point of view is:

$$\log(CG_{dt}^O) = \beta_1 \log(CG_{dt-1}^O) + \beta_2 \log(V_{IMS_{dt}}) + \beta_3 \log(V_{IMS_{dt-1}}) + \beta_4 \log(P_{IMS_{dt}}) + \beta_5 \log(P_{IMS_{dt-1}}) + \sum_{d=1}^6 \gamma_d DTUR_d + u_{dt} \quad (3)$$

The variable GC_{dt}^O measures the intensity of seasonality from the point of view of supply and for each of the tourist destinations, ($d = 1, 2, \dots, 6$), throughout the period under analysis, which goes from 2001 to 2019; ($t = 1, 2, \dots, 19$). Thus, there are 114 observations for the variable GC_{dt}^O . The variables $V_{IMS_{dmt}}$, $P_{IMS_{dmt}}$ and $DTUR_d$ have been explained previously.

From the economic point of view, the regression coefficient of the variable *number of travellers in the hotel establishments subsidised by Imsero* is expected to show a negative sign, indicating that the seasonality of the supply is reduced in the face of an increase in travellers. The regression coefficient that affects the variable *value of the subsidy* is expected to also be negative, since increasing subsidies would produce a greater supply for hotel establishments, causing a decrease in the intensity of seasonality.

4. Results

Demand

Initial results of the evolution of tourism activity suggest that both the group of foreign travellers and domestic travellers have maintained a high secular trend which has grown homogeneously throughout the entire period analysed, apart from the years 2009 and 2010 (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Number of Travellers in hotel establishments in Spain

Source: compiled by the authors using data from INE.

Table 1. Gini coefficient of total travellers in hotel establishments in Spain

	Spain	Andalusia	Balearic Islands	Canary islands	Catalonia	Valencian Community	Murcia Region
2008	0.15	0.15	0.42	0.04	0.19	0.14	0.10
2009	0.16	0.16	0.42	0.05	0.19	0.14	0.12
2010	0.16	0.16	0.44	0.06	0.19	0.15	0.11
2011	0.17	0.16	0.46	0.05	0.21	0.16	0.12
2012	0.17	0.16	0.46	0.04	0.19	0.17	0.11
2013	0.18	0.17	0.46	0.05	0.19	0.17	0.13
2014	0.18	0.17	0.47	0.05	0.19	0.16	0.11
2015	0.17	0.16	0.46	0.04	0.19	0.16	0.12
2016	0.17	0.15	0.45	0.04	0.19	0.15	0.11
2017	0.16	0.15	0.45	0.04	0.19	0.15	0.11
2018	0.16	0.14	0.44	0.04	0.18	0.14	0.10
2019	0.16	0.14	0.45	0.04	0.18	0.14	0.11

Source: compiled by the authors using data from INE.

Analysis of seasonality for the total travellers in hotel establishments leads us to conclude that seasonality is significantly higher in the group of foreign travellers in Spain than in the group of national travellers. Interestingly, the intensity of seasonality throughout the period analysed, for the whole of Spain, has remained practically constant for all years in the period studied (see Figure 1 and Table 1).

The study of seasonality by tourist destination in Spain provides mixed results. Indeed, when analysing the average seasonality coefficient³ for the period studied for each of the six tourist destinations (see Table 2 and Figure 1), the tourist destination with the most marked seasonality is that of the Balearic Islands, followed by Catalonia. On the contrary, the Canary Islands tourist destination shows hardly any seasonality.

Figure 2. Average seasonality coefficient of total travellers

Source: compiled by the authors using data from INE.

Individual analysis of each of the tourist destinations shows that Andalusia has a lower intensity of seasonality than that registered for the average for Spain throughout the period analysed (see Table 1). The tourist destination of the Balearic Islands is characterised by high seasonality. It should be noted that the economic crisis of 2008 had a negative effect on seasonality with its intensity increasing from 2010 onwards in the three groups of tourists. In all the cases analysed, seasonality for this tourist destination represents a significant imbalance. For the tourist destination of the Canary Islands, seasonality is irrelevant. Catalonia is characterised by high seasonality. The Valencian Community tourist destination is characterised as showing seasonality is lower than the

³ Not to be confused with the seasonal variation coefficient. The average seasonality coefficient attempts to quantify the average seasonal movement within each year for each of the months considered in relation to the expected trend value.

average seasonality registered for Spain. Lastly, the Murcia Region tourist destination is characterised as having a seasonal intensity lower than the average intensity of Spain.

Looking more closely at the study of the evolution of seasonality, from the perspective of demand, a model is specified to test whether the evolution of seasonality in the different destinations presents some pattern. A model is specified to study the β -Convergence (Barro & Sala-Martin, 1992) for each of the tourist destinations, through the following equation:

$$\text{Log}(GC_{at}) - \text{log}(GC_{at-1}) = \omega + \beta \text{log}(GC_{at-1}) + u_{at} \quad (4)$$

Table 2. β -Convergence of the demand in each tourist destination

	ω	β -Convergence	Coefficient of determination
Andalusia	-0.25	-0.13	0.08
Balearic Islands	-0.19***	-0.25***	0.38
Canary Islands	-1.01	-0.33	0.14
Catalonia	-0.74**	-0.45**	0.17
Valencian Community	-0.29	-0.16	0.11
Murcia Region	-0.61	-0.27	0.13

Note: ** and *** probabilistically significant at 95% and 99%, respectively.

Source: compiled by the authors.

The results of the estimates of equation (4), shown in Table 2, suggest that the Balearic Islands is the only tourist destination that presents a clear pattern of seasonality, statistically significant, at 99% probability. Catalonia shows a significant pattern at 95% probability and the other destinations considered do not exhibit behaviour which reflects a seasonal pattern.

Figure 3. Number of hotel establishments that are open in Spain.

Source: compiled by the authors using data from INE.

Supply

The supply indicator, the number of hotel establishments that are open in Spain shows a very regular pattern in its behaviour throughout the period analysed, which is indicative of the presence of seasonality (see Figure 3).

The study of seasonality, using the Gini coefficient, indicates that seasonality is very high in the tourist destination of the Balearic Islands. Indeed, when analysing the average seasonality coefficient of the period under study of the six tourist destinations (see Figure 4), the only destination that presents a marked seasonality is seen to be the Balearic Islands. The other tourist destinations show practically no seasonality.

Figure 4. Coefficient of average seasonality of hotel establishments that are open

Source: compiled by the authors using data from INE.

Table 3 shows the evolution of the GC for the indicator supply i.e., the number of hotel establishments that are open. For the whole of Spain, this indicator shows hardly any seasonality. However, by tourist destinations, the only destination with high seasonality is the Balearic Islands. In addition, from an evolutionary point of view, seasonality in the Balearic Islands is seen to increase up until 2015, stabilising thereafter.

To look in more detail at the evolution of seasonality, from the supply perspective, the β -Convergence is estimated for each of the six tourist destinations considered. In effect, equation (4) is used to check whether the evolution of seasonality in the different destinations presents some pattern. The results of the estimates of equation (4), presented in Table 4, suggest that the only tourist destination that presents a seasonal pattern, statistically significant at 99% probability, is the Balearic Islands. Interestingly, the tourist destination of the Canary Islands is characterised by presenting a totally volatile

behaviour, since the β -Convergence is greater than 1. Lastly, the other destinations considered do not present seasonal behaviour.

Table 3. Gini coefficient of the hotel establishments that are open by destination

	Spain	Andalusia	Balearic Islands	Canary Islands	Catalonia	Valencian Community	Murcia Region
2008	0.06	0.04	0.38	0.01	0.09	0.04	0.04
2009	0.06	0.05	0.38	0.01	0.09	0.04	0.04
2010	0.06	0.05	0.40	0.03	0.09	0.04	0.04
2011	0.07	0.05	0.42	0.01	0.09	0.06	0.05
2012	0.07	0.05	0.42	0.01	0.09	0.06	0.05
2013	0.07	0.05	0.41	0.01	0.08	0.06	0.05
2014	0.07	0.05	0.42	0.01	0.09	0.06	0.05
2015	0.08	0.06	0.42	0.01	0.09	0.06	0.06
2016	0.07	0.06	0.42	0.01	0.09	0.06	0.05
2017	0.07	0.06	0.41	0.01	0.09	0.06	0.05
2018	0.07	0.06	0.40	0.01	0.08	0.06	0.05
2019	0.07	0.06	0.40	0.01	0.09	0.06	0.05

Source: compiled by the authors using data from INE.

Table 4. β -Convergence of the supply in each tourist destination

	ω	β -Convergence	Coefficient of determination
Andalusia	-0,32	-0,07	0,07
Balearic Islands	-0,15***	-0,18***	0,45
Canary Islands	-5,17***	-1,09***	0,58
Catalonia	-0,19	-0,10	0,13
Valencian Community	-0,59	-0,21	0,12
Murcia Region	-0,88	-0,33	0,14

Note: *** probabilistically significant at 99%.

Source: compiled by the authors.

The indicators related to administration of supply (number of places available and hired personnel) generally show seasonality, except for the Canary Islands. When comparing the results of Table 3 with those of Table 5, it can be concluded that, in general, the establishments remain open despite the drop in demand. However, the seasonality of the demand leads to adaptation of the resources used, such as the places available.

Econometric model

As indicated in the previous section, two econometric models are specified that attempt to contrast whether the Imerso Social Tourism Programme has contributed to a reduction of seasonality in tourism activity in Spain.

From the point of view of demand, the objective variable used is that of the seasonal intensity of the number of total travellers in hotel establishments. The degree or

intensity of seasonality of each of the tourist destinations is measured through the natural logarithm of the six proposed seasonality coefficients.

The results of the estimations of the econometric models of demand, through equation (2), are⁴:

$$\log(GC_{dt}^D) = 0.67^{***} \log(GC_{dt-1}^D) - 0.07^{***} \log(V_{IMS_{dt}}) + 0.01 \log(V_{IMS_{dt-1}}) + 0.11 \log(P_{IMS_{dt}}) + 0.01 \log(P_{IMS_{dt-1}})$$

5)

Table 5. Gini coefficient of the number of places available

	Spain	Andalusia	Balearic islands	Canary islands	Catalonia	Valencian community	Murcia Region
2008	0.11	0.06	0.39	0.01	0.17	0.04	0.07
2009	0.11	0.07	0.41	0.01	0.17	0.05	0.07
2010	0.11	0.08	0.42	0.03	0.16	0.05	0.07
2011	0.11	0.08	0.42	0.01	0.16	0.06	0.07
2012	0.11	0.09	0.43	0.01	0.16	0.07	0.07
2013	0.12	0.11	0.44	0.01	0.16	0.07	0.08
2014	0.12	0.11	0.45	0.00	0.16	0.07	0.07
2015	0.12	0.11	0.45	0.01	0.16	0.07	0.07
2016	0.12	0.11	0.44	0.01	0.16	0.07	0.07
2017	0.12	0.11	0.44	0.01	0.16	0.07	0.08
2018	0.12	0.11	0.44	0.01	0.16	0.07	0.08
2019	0.12	0.11	0.44	0.01	0.16	0.07	0.08

Source: compiled by the authors using data from INE.

The results suggest that the seasonality of all types of travellers staying in hotel establishments shows a high inertia and, in addition, the number of travellers using the Imsero programme in periods of low demand and the price of trips financed by Imsero are probabilistically significant.

The number of travellers using the Imsero programme therefore contributes to a decrease in the behaviour of seasonality. The negative sign of the coefficient of the variable number of travellers subsidised by the Imsero programme is statistically significant, with a probability of 99%, which indicates that the higher the number of travellers, the greater would be the decrease in tourist seasonality. However, the price of the trips subsidised by Imsero have a positive influence on seasonality, indicating that a decrease in the value of the subsidy does not translate into a fall in demand and therefore an increase in seasonality, as might be expected, but rather it decreases the seasonality of tourist destinations. The explanation for this sign and the reduction in seasonality lies in the fact that the demand from the beneficiaries of the programme is inelastic and so, despite the decrease in the value of the subsidy, the demand for travel remains high and the beneficiaries are prepared to pay more for their holidays.

⁴ In equation (5) (***) indicates that the coefficient is probabilistically significant at 99%.

Since 2012, the value of the subsidy offered by Imsero has been steadily decreasing while the demand from potential beneficiaries has not, and so the reduction of seasonality has been maintained. Lastly, it should be noted that the elasticity, in absolute value, is slightly higher for prices than for the number of travellers subsidised by Imsero.

The results of the estimations of the econometric models of supply, equation (3), using the number of hotel establishments that are open, are⁵:

$$\log(CG_{dt}^o) = 0.41^{***} \log(CG_{dt-1}^o) - 0.41 \log(V_{IMS_{dt}}) - 0.19 \log(V_{IMS_{dt-1}}) + 0.21 \log(P_{IMS_{dt}}) + 0.22 \log(P_{IMS_{dt-1}}) \quad (6)$$

The results show a high inertia, meaning that the price of the trips subsidised by Imsero and the number of travellers benefitting from the programme in periods of low tourist demand does not influence the seasonality of the supply, since they are not statistically significant, with a probability of 95%. Therefore, neither the value of the subsidy nor the number of subsidised trips affects the seasonality of the tourist activity. The reason for this is because the supply does not really respond to the value of the subsidy or to the number of places that Imsero assigns in each programme.

The scarce seasonality in the supply is due to the fact that tourist agents themselves, to the extent of their possibilities, adapt the offer to the existing demand in periods of low tourism activity. In this way, tourism entrepreneurs, in general, keep their establishments open and adapt their offer to demand by modifying the degree of occupancy and the personnel hired. Only in the Balearic Islands, where the level of foreign tourism is high, does supply present high seasonality as well as demand.

In conclusion, the results of the econometric models suggest that the Imsero Social Tourism Programme is effective in reducing the seasonality of tourism activity in Spain, from the perspective of demand. However, further improvement could be made by increasing the number of places made available, since the number of applications tends to be triple the number of places on offer. Similarly, the value of the subsidy offered by the Imsero programme has almost halved from the beginning of the period under study to the present, while the spending by Imsero users has increased by 60%, with no reduction in applications to the programme. This suggests that more places could be offered and, although this would require an increase in the budget of the programme, given the economic and social benefits derived from the programme, its expansion and further development merits consideration.

4. Conclusions

Seasonality in tourism activity in Spain is a problem that has been increasing year on year. In some Spanish tourist destinations, such as the Balearic Islands, the situation is particularly acute.

⁵ In equation (6) (***) indicates that the coefficient is probabilistically significant at 99%.

The results of the econometric models suggest that the Imsero Social Tourism Programme is effective in reducing the seasonality of tourism activity in Spain, from the perspective of demand. Companies should also instigate campaigns to attract retired people and/or people with free time to travel outside of the high season. Even if the trips are not subsidised by Imsero, a good marketing campaign, with attractive and competitive prices, would attract the attention and interest of the target public.

Local authorities could promote other types of tourism, different from the season-driven beach and sun holidays, such as congress and/or urban tourism. These alternatives would require, among other things, large venues for conferences, an interesting offer of museums, an adequate public transport system as well as infrastructures that administrations must ensure are adapted to meet specific needs.

Another possible way to reduce seasonality could be achieved through price discrimination in hotel establishments in periods of low demand, in order to increase demand. Hotel rates do not present, in general, a high seasonality. If prices were better adapted to demand, that is, if they were reduced in periods of low demand, they could potentially attract more tourists.

Finally, it should be noted that the health crisis caused by Covid-19 led to the cancellation of the 2019-2020 and 2020-2021 programs. However, the 2022-2023 program has been re-established with a significant increase in the supply of places compared to the 2018-2019 program; specifically, an offer totalling of 918,504 places is foreseen. A possible limitation of the new tourist policy measures, to mitigate seasonality, is that the authorities have frozen the prices of the subsidies. This fact could cause a limitation of the validity of the new program by reducing the places offered. Nonetheless, the new program has received good reception from the beneficiaries and, although there is still no data to assess its scope, it is expected to continue mitigating the seasonality of tourist activity.

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